

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

FREE AND ENLIGHTENED CONSENT

Title: Correlating Code Smells and Refactorings in the Elixir functional language

Institutions: DCC/ICEx/UFMG and DPI/CCE/UFV

Responsible researchers:

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Associate professor at the Department of Computer Science at UFMG

This "Free and Enlightened Consent" contains information about our research. If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask the responsible researchers.

Evaluation goals: This study aims to understand developers' perspectives on the ability of refactoring strategies for Elixir to remove code smells from programs implemented in this language

Survey information: We will ask you questions about your demographics, positions held, experience with Elixir, and your perception of code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir (i.e., the completeness of the removals).

Data collection and use: The data will be collected through this Google Form. It is estimated that each participant will need a maximum of 60 minutes to complete the answers. This data will be used to promote good practices to improve the quality of code implemented in Elixir. The identities of all participants, as well as their responses, will be kept confidential. You may choose to receive the preliminary results of the study, with the anonymity of data and participants preserved. The results will be published and presented at conferences and scientific journals without revealing the identity of the participants.

If you decide not to participate in the research: You are free to refuse to participate or withdraw your consent at any time. Your decision will not affect any relationship with the evaluators, professors, or the institution responsible for this research.

Compensation: Your participation is voluntary and unpaid. In addition, you will not be charged for participating in this research.

If you have any problems or any other questions about the research or the ethical aspects of this study: You can contact Lucas Vegi at any time at lucas.vegi@ufv.br.

Risks and measures to minimize them: When answering the questions, you may feel uncomfortable with questions that can bring back bad memories, fear of not knowing the answer, or even being identified. If you feel uncomfortable, you can pause completing the questionnaire and withdraw from participation at any time. The guarantee of data confidentiality ensured by the researchers is limited to the privacy policies of the virtual environment used for data collection (Google Forms). According to Brazilian legislation (Art. 9 of Resolution nº 510/16 of the National Health Council), in case of any damages resulting from your participation in this research, you will have the right to be compensated, under the terms of the Law.

Benefits: This research aims to promote good practices for improving the quality of systems implemented in Elixir, thus justifying its risks.

This survey will be carried out entirely remotely. In this way, [this consent term will be made available in digital copy through this Google Form](#). A copy of this digital consent will be kept by the responsible researchers and you will receive a digital copy via email after signing the term.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

E-mail *

Seu e-mail

Your full name: *

Sua resposta

Free and Enlightened Consent (voluntary agreement) *

I declare that I have read the document mentioned above and that I agree to participate as a volunteer, authorizing the anonymous use of the data generated by my participation for the academic purposes described above.

Avançar

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Limpar formulário

Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Demographic questions

Select your country: *

Your city: *

Elixir experience time: *

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- More than 3 years

How many different projects have you participated in using Elixir? *

- Only one project
- Between 2 and 4 projects
- More than 4 projects

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Survey on Correlating Smells and Refactorings in Elixir

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Perceptions on code smell removal using refactoring strategies in Elixir

In previous studies, we cataloged [35 code smells](#) and [82 refactorings](#) tailored for Elixir. **In the present work, we are proposing practical guidelines for removing code smells in Elixir using sequences of refactorings specific to the language.**

For each code smell you are asked to evaluate, we will present the refactorings useful for its removal and explain their specific applications. These refactorings are listed in the order in which they should be performed when they are part of a sequence of operations. Specifically, when a refactoring should be applied on its own, it is listed with a bullet point (i.e., •). Conversely, when a refactoring is part of a sequence of operations, it is numbered to indicate its order (e.g., 1., 2., etc.).

Therefore, based on your experience, please answer the following questions for each presented smell:

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings removes this smell?

- Please rate the degree to which the refactoring sequence removes the code smell
- (1 = the refactoring sequence absolutely does not help remove the smell; 5 = the refactoring sequence completely removes the smell)

Notes:

- Each smell and refactoring is accompanied by a short description and a link with code examples.

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Long parameter list\]](#) smell? *

In a functional language like Elixir, functions tend to be pure and therefore do not access or manipulate values outside their scopes. Since the input values of these functions are just their parameters, it is natural to expect that functions with a long list of parameters be created to keep them pure. However, when this list has more than three or four parameters, the function's interface becomes confusing and prone to errors during use. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): If a function parameter for some reason is never used, it can be removed using this refactoring.
 - [\[Reorder parameter\]](#): When a function has a long list of parameters that reduces its readability, we can at least reorder the list into a more logical sequence to improve clarity.
1. [\[Grouping parameters in tuple\]](#): If a function has sequential and related parameters in its list, these parameters can be grouped into a *tuple*, thus reducing the length of the list.
 2. [\[From tuple to struct\]](#): A *tuple* used to group parameters can eventually be replaced by a *struct* using this refactoring.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Accessing non-existent map/struct fields\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when *struct* or *map* fields are accessed dynamically, which may result in *nil* values that can be ambiguous and lead developers to introduce bugs. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Default value for an absent key in a Map\]](#): When trying to access the value of a key from a *Map* dynamically, it is not possible to determine if a key is non-existent or if it has an associated *nil* value. This refactoring can eliminate the smell, as the ambiguity in the returns of dynamic accesses will no longer occur after its application.
 - [\[Introduce pattern matching over a parameter\]](#): If the smell instance occurs in the function signature, such as in a guard clause, we can use this refactoring to extract the value of that field and then use it in the guard. This way, we can clearly determine if a field does not exist or if it simply has an associated *nil* value.
 - [\[Simplifying checks by using truthness condition\]](#): Optionally, when using dynamic access to fields of a *Map* and needing to return a default value for non-existent fields or those associated with *nil*, we can perform this refactoring to solve this issue, thus producing cleaner code.
 - [\[Explicit a double boolean negation\]](#): Optionally, if we are using double boolean negation to check if a dynamically accessed field in a *Map* exists, this refactoring can improve code readability by replacing the unintuitive logic with helper functions that utilize pattern matching.
1. [\[Struct field access elimination\]](#): Optionally, if accesses to the same field, whether it exists or not, occur many times within a function, we can use this refactoring to replace these accesses with a temporary variable responsible for storing the value of that field.
 2. [\[Equality guard to pattern matching\]](#): Optionally, when a temporary variable extracted from a *struct* field is only used in an equality comparison in a guard, extracting and using that variable is unnecessary, as we can perform that equality comparison directly with pattern matching. To do this, we can use this refactoring.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Unrelated multi-clause function\]](#) smell? *

Using multi-clause functions in Elixir, to group functions of the same name, is not a code smell in itself. However, due to the great flexibility provided by this programming feature, some developers may abuse the number of guard clauses and pattern matches to group *unrelated* functionality. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): A possible solution to this smell is to use this refactoring to break up the business rules that are mixed into several different simple functions. Specifically, groups of clauses from the original function that share related functionalities can be renamed with an identical name, thus forming a new multi-clause function.
 2. [\[Function clauses to/from case clauses\]](#): Optionally, after renaming the groups of related clauses, thus creating new multi-clause functions, these multi-clause functions can be transformed into single-clause functions by mapping function clauses into clauses of case statements.
- [\[Moving a definition\]](#): When unrelated clauses of a multi-clause function differ to the point where they do not make sense in the current module, these clauses can be moved to other modules where they fit better, thus making the code more cohesive.
 - [\[Struct guard to matching\]](#): Optionally, when some of the clauses of a multi-clause function use a guard clause involving the functions `is_struct/1` or `is_struct/2`, we can use this refactoring to simplify the pattern matching performed by these function clause's signature.
 - [\[Equality guard to pattern matching\]](#): Optionally, when an unnecessary temporary variable is extracted from a `struct`'s field in a clause of a multi-clause function only to be used in an equality comparison in a guard, we can use this operation to simplify the pattern matching performed by this function clause's signature.
 - [\[Simplifying guard sequences\]](#): Optionally, when a clause of a multi-clause function contains redundant logical propositions, we can simplify the pattern matching performed by this function clause's signature through the transformation carried out by this refactoring.
 - [\[Converts guards to conditionals\]](#): Optionally, when what differentiates the clauses of a multi-clause function are only the logical checks performed in their guard clauses, we can use this refactoring to replace all guards with traditional conditionals, creating only one clause for the function.
 - [\[Simplifying pattern matching with nested structs\]](#): Optionally, when using pattern matching to perform deep extraction in nested `structs` passed as parameters to a clause of a multi-clause function, we may create unnecessarily messy and hard-to-understand code. With this refactoring, we can simplify this kind of extraction by performing pattern matching only on the outermost `struct` in the nesting, instead of matching patterns with very internal `structs`.
 - [\[Remove unnecessary calls to length/1\]](#): Optionally, when unnecessary calls to the function `length/1` are used in guard clauses to differentiate the pattern matching performed by different clauses of a multi-clause function, we can replace these calls with direct pattern matching on the parameter list of the function clauses, thereby improving code efficiency.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Complex else clauses in with\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when *with* statements handle all of their error clauses in a single *else* block. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [\[Extract function\]](#): When an *else* clause in a *with* statement is used to handle different types of errors that may occur during the execution of the *with* clauses, the code can become confusing. To address this issue, we can use this refactoring to transform expressions in the *with* clauses into separate private functions. Each of these private functions will handle a specific error type, decentralizing the error-handling task.
 2. [\[Remove dead code\]](#): After extracting the new functions responsible for decentralizing error handling, the *with* statement will no longer need an *else* clause. Therefore, we can use this refactoring to remove the *else* clause.
- [\[Remove redundant last clause in "with"\]](#): Optionally, if the last clause of the *with* statement used to chain operations is redundant, we can use this refactoring to make the code less verbose and more readable.
 - [\[Moving "with" clauses without pattern matching\]](#): Optionally, if the *with* statement does not perform pattern matching in the first and/or last clauses, we can use this refactoring to make the code more idiomatic and readable.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta _____

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [Unnecessary macros](#) smell? *

This smell refers to the use of *macros* in situations where functions or *structs* would be more appropriate. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [Inline macro](#): When code is implemented as a *macro* but could be implemented as a conventional function in Elixir, we can use this refactoring to remove this smell, improving the readability of the code.
1. [Extract function](#): When creating a *macro* is unavoidable, but part of it could be implemented as a conventional named function, we can extract this part of the *macro*'s code and encapsulate it into a conventional function, which the *macro* will then call. This approach improves code organization and readability while leveraging the *macro* for its specific role.
 2. [Moving a definition](#): After extracting the function, it may eventually be necessary to move it to another module to make the code more cohesive.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [Using exceptions for control-flow](#) smell? *

This smell refers to code that forces developers to handle exceptions for control-flow. Exception handling itself does not represent a code smell, but this should not be the only alternative available to developers to handle an error in client code. When developers have no freedom to decide if an error is exceptional or not, this is considered a code smell. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

1. [Rename an identifier](#): To prevent a library function from always forcing third-party code to handle an error as an exception, we can initially rename the original function, adding a trailing *!* at the end of its name. In Elixir, there is a convention where a *!* (i.e., *trailing* or *bang*) at the end of a function name indicates that it may raise an exception.
 2. [Introduce a temporary duplicate definition](#): After renaming the original function by adding a *!* at the end of its name, we can use this refactoring to duplicate the renamed original function. This copy should have the original function's name, without the *!* at the end. Instead of raising exceptions, it should return data in the *tuple* format (i.e., `{:ok, _}` or `{:error, msg}`). The message provided in the error *tuple* should be the same as the one originally displayed in the exception version.
 3. [Folding against a function definition](#): Finally, we can use the present refactoring to change the *bang* variant (i.e., the original function that raises an exception, with *!* at the end of its name). With this transformation, the raising version is implemented on top of the non-raising version of the code.
-
1. [Introduce processes](#): Another possibility for removing this smell is, if the module where the function that raises an exception is not a process (e.g., *GenServer* or *Task*), we can use this refactoring to transform the module into a process.
 2. [Moving error-handling mechanisms to supervision trees](#): When a process is using defensive programming (i.e., `try.rescue`) to handle exceptions and even control the execution flow, we can use this refactoring to eliminate this type of handling, transitioning instead to the "Let it crash" style.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

Do you agree that this sequence of refactorings remove the [\[Speculative generality\]](#) smell? *

This smell occurs when a code has fragments that were implemented in order to give it flexibility in the future, but in practice they end up not being useful because they are never used. In Elixir, this smell can be felt in *modules* not used anywhere in the code, *functions* that are never called or even in functions with *parameters* defined with default values and which do not have calls that inform different values for these parameters. Code with this smell is unnecessarily large and more difficult to maintain. To remove this smell, we apply the following refactorings:

- [\[Inline function\]](#): Use this refactoring to get rid of unused functions or even unnecessarily created ones.
- [\[Inline macro\]](#): Similarly to the previous refactoring, use this operation to eliminate unused macros or those that were unnecessarily created.
- [\[Add or remove a parameter\]](#): Functions with unused parameters should be reviewed using this refactoring.
- [\[Rename an identifier\]](#): Functions with abstract names should be renamed using more specific names that reflect their current task, rather than potential future tasks they might perform.
- [\[Behaviour inlining\]](#): Unnecessary delegation/generalization caused by the excessive use of Elixir's *behaviour* can be removed with this refactoring.
- [\[Remove dead code\]](#): In general, any code created unnecessarily to support future features that are never implemented can be refactored using this operation.
- [\[Eliminate single branch\]](#): When a conditional is created to potentially provide different treatments for different types of data but actually provides the same treatment to all, we can simplify the code by removing unnecessary complexity.

(1 = absolutely does not remove the smell; 5 = completely removes the smell)

	1	2	3	4	5
Removal	<input type="radio"/>				

Please justify your answer, especially if you rated it below 4 for the previous smell:

Sua resposta

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* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

Final remarks

Please add here any comment about our work and survey:

Sua resposta

Do you want to receive the preliminary results of this study? *

- Yes
- No

Uma cópia das suas respostas será enviada para o endereço de e-mail fornecido

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